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Loves Singers*

Warren Jones

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A Natural Nonpareil

Warren Jones performs with the world's greatest singers in the most prestigious halls. Whether at the White House, the Met, or in Salzburg, his collaboration is as infectious as it is intuitive. And he has a unique view of what it means to play the piano.

The phone rings, and the caller tries to camouflage her voice. But she makes a single mistake. She inhales. And in that instant Warren Jones calls her by name. An incredible ear? Yes, of course. But also an uncanny empathy for those he partners. The list is an international litany—Marilyn Horne, Håkan Hagegård, Samuel Ramey, Dame Kiri Te Kanawa, Tatiana Troyanos, Martti Talvela, Kathleen Battle, Barbara Bonney, Ruth Ann Swenson, Judith Blegen, Harolyn Blackwell, Carol Vaness ...

This lanky, likable, good-humored, All-American storyteller strides across the stages at Carnegie Hall, Lincoln Center, Teatro alla Scala, the Opéra Bastille, Wigmore Hall, Ravinia, Tanglewood, and the Vienna Konzerthaus with the same jaunty enthusiasm he displayed as the bass drummer in his North Carolina marching band. He loves to make music with others.

And he loves singers. Our far-ranging conversation took place in Fort Worth, where Jones was serving as a Cliburn Competition juror. References to tone, breathing, languages, vibrato, pronunciation, and vocal repertoire were never far from the center of attention. But Jones was just as likely to explore life's deepest mysteries. He is open to epiphanies.

Even though our time together ended with an impromptu performance of a rag he had recently played for the assembled judges of the Supreme Court, it began with a conventional query.

What would you like to be called? Some people want to be called collaborative artist, some want to be known as accompanist ...

I'd like to be known as a pianist. I play the piano in several different arrangements—sometimes by myself, sometimes with instrumentalists, a lot of the time with singers. But it's always playing the piano. So I'd like to be called a pianist.

Now, though, you work mostly with singers?

I do. But you have to do all the other things.

And continue to do them?

Yes. You have to. The business and the culture wants to pigeon-hole each of us because it's easier that way. But if you pigeon-hole yourself, very quickly all of your sensibilities begin to shrink and wither. One must constantly stretch out, play a Brahms Quintet, a Beethoven trio, do new sonatas for flute and piano. And it's also very important to continue to study and perform solo music. This year I had the chance to play solo about four or five times, which I gladly took each time because that's something that's just part of my continuing education.

For a lot of people, playing the piano well is a finished product. To me it's an entry-level skill, because you have to play the piano fabulously well to do collaborative work. There's so much other stuff to pay attention to that you don't have time to think about how to play. There are an infinite number of things you have to be concerned about other than your technique.

When did you realize you were going to have a career as a collaborative performer as well as a solo pianist?

I don't have any idea. I know when I was in college, I tried as much as I could to train myself to be a solo pianist or a teacher or a collaborator. And it quickly became apparent to me that I did not have the personality required to be just a solo pianist. That requires a huge amount of solitude and—in a good way—an egocentric approach to things. I don't have either of those. Although I envy egocentric people, I don't have *that* kind of egocentricity.

The bottom line is that I adore making music with other people. To me that is the most unbelievable fun, because I find things out about them that they could never tell me with words.

For instance ...

For a long time when people interviewed me, it's because they really wanted to know about the people I worked with. I was once asked, "What is Samuel Ramey really like?" I decided to have some fun with the interviewer. "Well," I said, "I know things about Samuel Ramey that no one else in the world knows, not even his wife. His ears perked up. "I know things that are so incredibly personal about him that you can't imagine." His ears perked up some more. "But, unfortunately, I cannot tell you a single one of them because they have to do with music. You can't know about these things unless you can play the piano."

When you're collaborating with somebody on stage, you quickly learn where they're comfortable, and which things they're afraid of doing. You know when they're exhilarated because they won. You know when something didn't go well, and they feel a little bit down. It's a very personal relationship.

And they know that about you, too.

Oh, yeah. It's entirely a two-way street.

Where are you from?

I was born in Washington DC, right down the road from the White House. We moved to North Carolina when I was five, and I went through school there. I went to a public high school out in the country, and had private music lessons. I was in the band and the chorus.

What did you play in the band?

All of the brass instruments, except trombone, and most of the woodwind instruments, except flute. And also some percussion. I was the biggest one, so I

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played bass drum and marched because I was the only one big enough to carry the bass drum. I think the bass drum is a gas. I didn't appreciate that until I played it. It is entirely the nerve center of the band. It is the basic rhythm of the whole thing. If the bass drum is there, the whole thing's going to be there; and if it's not, then nothing's going to be right. I enjoy being the nerve center of things.

Did you begin private music lessons early?

I gave my first public recital when I was five. It was pretty much a disaster. The next recital I played at six was also a disaster, but for very different reasons. But in neither of them did I stop because my teacher had told me that you *never* stop when you play in public. So it didn't cross my mind to stop.

Even at five you knew that the show had to go on.

I was playing a set of variations on Chopsticks, and the biggest bravura moment was a set of glissandi. My teacher had neglected to tell me exactly how you do that. I had just done it, somehow, with my thumbnail. In the performance, instead of putting my thumbnail on the key, I turned my hand sideways and caught the side of my thumb on the edge

of one of the white keys and literally slit it, like a knife would. The keys were quite bloody by the time I finished. But I kept going.

The second time I played in public, at six, I used the pedal. I had to slide out to the edge of the bench and sort of jab my legs at it. When I jabbed for the pedal the first time, instead of hitting the pedal, I hit the piano. It was an upright, and there was a large flower arrangement on the top. The piano rocked backwards, and then rocked forwards toward me. The flowers went flying off. I was drenched in water, and flowers were everywhere—flowers on the keys, flowers on me. The audience was in stitches. But I kept on going, because my teacher had told me not to stop. After these first two public performances, I haven't been rattled by anything.

Who was this teacher that made you so aware of not stopping in public?

Athlene Carter took me on when I was five. And I tell you that I was a real terror. I would frequently trap my sisters in their room after school, for example, and make them show me everything they learned at school that day before I would let them go.

This is before you, yourself, went to school?

Yes, when I was four and five. My sisters were studying piano. I figured out, without being able to read letters or numbers or anything, the five-finger system that they were studying for beginning piano even before I began to take lessons. Eventually, when I was in about the sixth grade, I went to study with a lady named Bess Gayle who had suffered early in her life with polio. She had crippling arthritis and scoliosis, and she was in a wheelchair. She never played the piano for me in any lesson. She was in her wheelchair, and she sat across the room from me and taught me

"The job is much more about how to handle people."

how to play the piano verbally by having me recognize sensations in my arms and back. She would say, "That sounds right. How does that feel?"

Smart lady:

She had played successfully on the radio, and had studied at Juilliard with Ernest Hutcheson. But she had no possibility of a career because of her infirmities and her gender. When I knew her, she had about 30 minutes that she could play each day. She would put her hands in hot wax in order to relax them. And then in 30 minutes of playing, her hands would be entirely frozen and gnarled. She was a pretty amazing lady. As a result, I never learned a whole lot of music. But what I learned, I learned really well. So by the time I left her and went off to college, I was fairly proficient.

What are your memories of the New England Conservatory?

One woman with whom I worked,

Gladys Miller, was a voice teacher. I worked with her five hours a day, five days a week. She pulled me aside one day during my senior year and said, "Warren, are you thinking about doing this for a living?" I said, "I don't know. It's a possibility." And she said, "Well, I want to tell you something. If you do this for a living, it's not enough that you like Schubert, or that you like Verdi, or Puccini, or Brahms, or that you like to play the piano for singers, or that you like singing, or that you like the human voice, that you like the lyricism, that you like opera, that you like art song, blah, blah, blah. None of those things are important. The first thing is to *love singers*. If you love singers, all the rest of it will come. And if you don't love singers, none of the rest of it will help."

And after the New England Conservatory?

I finished my formal education in San Francisco, working with Milton Salkind, who taught me a great deal about listen-

ing and about music and about hearing. Quite an amazing teacher.

When would you say your career began?

It's been going on so long that I don't have any idea. Early on, I don't think my father believed that I would do this. My father and mother came to Boston to see me play a Mozart D-minor concerto with Fiedler conducting. Symphony Hall was packed. I think that when they saw me come on the stage and play, and the people clapped, and no one threw anything at me, and it was a big success—I think they started to understand that I could do this, that this might be a way for me to make a living.

How did you get to work at the Met?

I had worked in the San Francisco opera for three years, but I was missing my family. So I wanted to go back to the East. Ideally I wanted to work at the Boston Opera because the Boston Opera season dovetailed with San Francisco. I could

work in both cities that way—be part of the year in the East, and part of the year in the West.

My audition at Boston was ... well, it would be a wild understatement to say that it flopped. I mean, the way that man crucified me was quite something. It was my first audition in the East. I sort of shrugged it off thinking, "Well, you have some good days and some bad days. This was not a good day for me." I subsequently auditioned for every opera company between Boston and Augusta, Georgia—and I mean, *every* one.

And Mr. Levine from the Metropolitan was the only person who offered me a job. Everyone else either put me off saying they didn't have a job right now, or told me flat out that they would not hire me. Levine hired me. I was the second youngest person ever hired at the Metropolitan for that job, and I had a wonderful time. I really did.

Were you a répétiteur?

Initially I was hired as a rehearsal pianist, and then I was promoted to assistant director.

What does that involve?

When I was there, the management had the good grace and sense to recognize what each member did well. The thing that I do well is to play and prompt and conduct rehearsals all at the same time—without the conductor being there, without the prompter being there—just me and the singers. It's a very intimate way to rehearse, very comfortable for the singers, and very good for the directors. I could do all those things, and that's what I usually did. I also coached, prepared people for opera performances.

You see, the job that I do even today—I told you before that playing the piano is the least of the things—the job is *much* more about how to handle people than it is how to handle the keyboard. It takes a

huge amount of people skill. And that's the knowledge and sensitivity about how people work, and how to work with them to have *them* get their best result.

How long were you there?

Ten years. Six full-time, then four years but not full-time. I had a meeting with Levine and explained that they treated me like a prince, that I could not possibly have a complaint, that I loved the job—but I wanted to play the piano in public, and I was not having enough chance to do that. He looked at me and said, "Go do it. We'll work it out. We'll figure out the details." And that's what we did.

Do singers approach you, or do you seek them out?

When people come to study music, eventually they will learn that they are studying about life.

It's very much by word of mouth. It's an incredibly small profession. Word gets around, very fast—good and bad. Singers sit around and talk to each other. It's sort of like men always wonder what women are talking about when they go to the women's room in a restaurant...the guys are left sitting at the table thinking, what are those women talking about? Well, singers sit around and have that kind of discussion about the people they're working with.

Do you think that's just true of singers? Wouldn't it be equally true, for example, with string players?

It may be, but I think singers have a peculiar set of neuroses and characteristics that bind them together much, much tighter than instrumentalists. And I mean *much* tighter. The unknown qualities of singing, which are so incredibly mysterious, make them into a fairly tight-knit group. It's quite something.

By "unknown qualities" you're talking about technique? How it's done?

No. You hear your voice on a tape recorder. It doesn't sound like your voice, right? Well, can you imagine if you never

ever heard what you sound like? If you had to rely entirely on other people to give you feedback? Well, when opera singers are singing at full volume, they cannot hear anything else. It's coming so much through their inner ear, on the backside of their eardrum, that literally it's not possible for a sound to come in from the other side. They cannot hear when they're singing at full volume. If they're just singing easily, they can hear what's going on. But if they're really letting loose, they don't hear very well, and they rely on people like me to guide them. It's an amazing exercise of trust. It requires a bond unlike what any violin player has with a pianist. It's an incredible—what's the word?—it's like an emotional and psychic bond.

You mean symbiosis?

Yes, exactly.

You're putting a very positive spin on what I have heard other people who work with singers put more negatively.

It is a lifetime work to understand the signals that a singer sends out in performing. A fiddle player, for example, sends out an entirely different set of signals in a performance, and some people spend their life learning that set of signals. There are not a whole lot of people who understand both sets.

Do you really think it's that strikingly different—the relationship between a pianist who works with singers, and a pianist who works with instrumentalists?

Yes. Singers' psyches are different.

You said you wanted to be called a pianist. Let's talk about your feelings and ideas about being a pianist.

I played the piano, in public, before I could read words. It's just part of me. To me, playing the piano is subconscious. I don't have any sensation of touching the keys. I don't have any sensation of touching the pedal.

Ever?

No.

You become so totally absorbed in the music-making process itself?

Right. It's something that just happens. I have a very good picture in my brain about the piano. I think of it as a fairly

simple shape, with very wide industrial tolerances, compared to modern industry. It's a very crude machine. It really is. And it has few working parts. It's wooden. How many machines do you know that are made of wood these days? Wood and felt and metal and a little bit of plastic in some modern ones. But it's basically primitive. And I feel like a battery. I come on the stage, and I hook myself onto it, and I make it run. And then I take myself off, and it sits there. Because I'm the battery that makes it run. And I really feel that way! I can link my feet and hands to it and make it run. It's like a circuit, the same way that a car has a battery and generator. The piano gives me energy, and I give the piano energy. Then

when you add in the people you may be making music with, it really becomes quite an electrical thing.

Sparks everywhere?

Exactly. There's a lot of energy going around for everybody, and I love that. I love that concept, and I love the sensation while doing it. There's all this stuff going on.

When you go to a voice recital, the first thing you notice is the quality of the tone coming out of the person's mouth. Yet I'm amazed by how many people ignore that in assessing their own pianism and the pianism of others. For me, the tone—the nature of the tone—is the bottom of the bottom of the basement. You must hear the tone quality.

You may open your eyes and see what's going on on-stage, but you heard it already in the nature of the tone. That's quite something to me—how we can project ourselves in the nature and the quality of the tone.

There's a wide margin of subjectivity, though. I can respond favorably to someone's tone, but the person sitting next to me may not like it.

I like the fact that when I play a concert, I have no control over how people hear it—that people can hear 14, 15, 16, or 83 million different things. That's comforting to me. If they all heard the same message, I would think that something was seriously wrong.

I am constantly fascinated by the psychology of playing the piano. Each time you press the key down, you have a result. You have an infinite number of results in the course of a

Jones, working with Hi-Myung Choo, at the Music Academy of the West.

performance. You play an instrument that is entirely unforgiving, because when you press the key down, that's all you can do. So you must, immediately, accept the result. You don't have time to sit there and argue with yourself. And that's not only if you make a mistake. It's also if you do something that's quite beautiful. Some of my most aggravating mistakes in public occurred when I congratulated myself because I played something nicely—and then promptly messed up the next phrase. The concept of self-acceptance, which is what it is—of doing it, accepting it, and going on to the next thing—is one of the most valuable lessons.

Flute players, for example, can sustain a pitch, change the pitch, add vibrato, take it away. They can do so many different things to the note. A violinist has the whole length of the bow. A sculptor has years in the studio to change a work before the public sees it. But we have no time, *no time*. The courage it takes to play the piano in public, that's quite something!

But even if you can't change the tone quality of the key you just pushed down, you can sometimes affect the perception of that tone by other things that you do with your left hand, or with the pedal, for instance.

But all that's predicated on accepting the initial result and playing with it, because you can't do anything with that result. The first thing is to accept—and that's a very good life lesson.

Do most pianists listen that carefully, actually give themselves a chance to hear what they're playing?

You know, that's the one thing we don't really knock ourselves out to teach.

For those who work with singers, learning languages must be an important part of their training and experience. Have you always been good at languages?

I started studying French when I was in high school. I had two years of French there, and two more years of French in college and undergraduate school. I also studied two years of German and two years of Italian.

I really began to learn after I was out of school because my teachers whetted my appetite so that I wanted to go out

Lisa Kohler

and do something. When I first went to work at the Metropolitan, I took a very intensive course in Italian. A lot of times I was working eight hours a day. And everything would be going on in Italian, and you just had to jump in and do it. You had to sink or swim. I chose to swim. And likewise with German.

My older sister's first mother-in-law was a woman from Hungary who spoke six languages, no English. Whenever I talked to her, I always spoke in German. She remarked one time—I'll always remember this—that you know as many worlds as the languages you speak. And that's very true. Because people have a different sensibility on account of languages. The culture is different. You can say the same thing, and it just comes out differently, it has a different flavor, a different reflection. You acquire a sensibility from speaking the languages. You appreciate all these different colors.

I used to believe that the reason I studied language was so that I would understand the pronunciation, so that I would have a good ensemble with a

singer. But now what I find important is to listen to the tone, to the nature, of the person's voice. To listen to timbre, to their vibrato. To sense a lot of things about their bodies which necessarily will also include the pronunciation. But the pronunciation is a very small part of that picture. If you get on to the vibrato speed—every singer has a different speed—you will have the right tempo all the time. You cannot be wrong.

It's something that I show my students, and they're amazed. And the singers are amazed, also, because when they're allowed to sing at their *tempo giusto*, the voice will do practically anything. But they cannot cram their voices into a tempo that someone else decides for them.

The French-Canadian tenor, Léopold Simoneau, was the first person that exposed me to that idea when I lived in San Francisco. He said, "Warren, remember there is no *tempo giusto* out there. There's a *tempo giusto* for every singer." We have to find that. On the other hand, fiddle players are much more flexible about the speed of the vibrato. It's expected that they have a huge flexibility in their bow speed, the bow weight, a lot of different things. It's part and parcel of their expression. Whereas a singer is gifted with that, and utilizes the gift to the best of his or her ability.

I guess, as a singer, you really can't control your vibrato, except perhaps to some degree.

Some people learn to. But it's very difficult. When you start to do that, you are either very foolish or incredibly advanced. And that's why those people sing in wide repertoires. Others do not, and are more or less married to a certain part of the singing repertory by the width of their vibrato, by the width of their sound, the core of their tone. Other people are successful at skinning out their voice to suit the music, or widening it. That's why singers have to continue to sing art songs and oratorio, because you need flexibility in the voice just as you do at the keyboard.

We've touched on several things that have to do with making a career as a collaborative pianist. But how do you make a career? You spoke of your field as being very small.

I've heard that, statistically, you have a better chance in this country of being a professional athlete than being a professional musician. That's a pretty daunting prospect. I'm talking about someone who earns money exclusively from performing—not teaching, not doing anything else, just playing concerts. You want a career as a collaborative pianist? If you're good, you'll have work. It's just as simple as that. We're talking about a small niche. There's a thirst for people who are good collaborative artists. There really is.

You're teaching now, training people to do what you do so well. What do you tell them?

Warren Jones on Record

- **Copland: Old American Songs; Ives: Songs**, with Samuel Ramey (bass). Decca/Argo 433 027-2
 - **Ev'ry Time We Say Goodbye**, with Samuel Ramey (bass). SONY Classical 68339
 - **Fauré Requiem and Songs**, with Barbara Bonney (soprano) and Håkan Hagegård (baritone). RCA Victor Red Seal 09026-68659-2
 - **The Flute Album**, with Michael Parloff (principal flute, Metropolitan Opera Orchestra). Ess.A.Y. Recordings CD1027
 - **Grieg Songs**, with Håkan Hagegård (baritone). RCA/BMG 09026-61630-2
 - **I carry your heart**, with Ruth Ann Swenson (soprano). EMI Classics 72435 56158-2-4
 - **Kathleen Battle at the Metropolitan Museum**, with Kathleen Battle (soprano). DG laser disc and videotape 072 289
 - **Marilyn Horne: Divas in Song**, with Marilyn Horne (mezzo-soprano) and others. RCA Victor 09026-62547-2
 - **Schubert: Die schöne Müllerin**, with Kevin McMillan (baritone). Dorian DOR-90162
 - **Songs of Stephen Paulus**, with Håkan Hagegård (baritone). Albany Records TROY 036-2
 - **Strange Hurt**, with Harolyn Blackwell (soprano). RCA Victor 09026-61944-2
 - **Where the Music Comes From: American Songs**, with Cynthia Haymon (soprano). Decca/Argo 436 117-2
- In preparation: **Songs of Brahms, Sibelius, and Stenhammer**, with Håkan Hagegård (baritone) for RCA/BMG. Including Brahms's op. 121 and op. 105 (complete)

As an educator, I'm convinced we don't have the time to teach anybody anything. I *guide* students, show them what they need to learn. When they're out of school—when, literally, they go through commencement—they can commence to learn.

How long have you been teaching?

I've been at Manhattan two years. I love teaching because, for me, teaching has little to do with music. It has a great deal

of the Chopin that he played—I don't know where it came from. It didn't come from any piano player that I had ever heard before.

Or the first time that I ever heard any Wagner. It was in San Francisco. I snuck into the opera house for a rehearsal and Miss [Jessye] Norman was singing. I had never heard her sing, and I'd never heard the music. I just burst into tears (I don't cry easily). It was other worldly, the effect that had on me. Or the first time I heard

through the forest, drunk. And I thought, "What does that mean?"

Then I had the chance to be at Hopewell Forge in Pennsylvania. I discovered a dugout inside a hill that had been where the charcoal maker was. And I got down on my stomach, which is what you had to do, and I crawled in, in the dirt. And I sat there (you couldn't stand up) on this hot day. People had lived in this thing! I just thought, *this* is why she was running through the forest, drunk—and she was the prettiest one.

Or—once I was standing in the basement, the bottom of the bottom of Biltmore House in North Carolina, a house that one of the Vanderbilts built, a sort of summer cottage, believe it or not. It has about 260 rooms. And the bottom of the bottom is where the servants of the servants lived and worked. The servants had servants! The cook didn't make the fire, for example. The fire was made by his servant. There's a little song called "Das verlassene Mägdlein." It says, "Early in the morning when the crow has called, I go to work. And the flames come up in the kitchen, and it's like they're burning inside me." I looked around and thought, it could be in *this* house. The lowest of the low of girls had been seduced by this man. She could easily be standing in *this* kitchen, making a fire in *that* stove. And I suddenly had the picture of what that song was about. How she must feel standing there looking out the window, and looking back and seeing flames come up, and thinking about the flame inside her. For me, the world is full of stuff like that that has to do with music.

You have to be open to it.

Let's go back to what I said about education. People today are not urged to be curious. They are fed everything that people think they need to know by any number of means: by television, radio, movies, pop magazines ... there is no sense of curiosity. If somehow they could become curious, they'd start to get on to all those things.

You provoke them into being curious, if you can.

It's a great choice of words—you *provoke* people into being curious. For me, the best part, you know, is the mystery. I love that! I love not knowing the answers all of the time. ❖

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to do with life. I never actually discuss their own life situations with my students. I'm not their psychoanalyst. We have chosen to work together in matters of music, but we're really talking about how they're living. They may not understand that initially. They may not understand that in the middle, perhaps not even at the end. But eventually they'll understand that how they play is a reflection of how they live. This is what I'm talking about—that when people come to study music, eventually they will learn that they are studying about life.

Who are some of your own ideals?

I heard Rubinstein play in public one time, and the tone that he made in some

Nilsson sing. I had never imagined a voice that was so overwhelming that I couldn't hear the orchestra. And she was not straining. It was just this pervasive total presence of her voice!

But a lot of my influences and experiences have been extramusical. Let me give you some examples. For instance, I read the last of the Keller songs by Wolf. I read the poem, and I didn't understand it at all. The music is just this crazy, unbelievable music. It has to do with a woman who was the best-looking girl in town, and she fastidiously refused every offer, thinking that she was going to get a better offer. Pretty soon people stopped asking. Now she's married to the charcoal maker, and she is running